

strong aya

A new, interdisciplinary, multi-stakeholder European network to improve healthcare services, research and outcomes for Adolescents and Young Adults with cancer.

The future of cancer therapy

Deliverable Report

WP1: Material for education and clinical implementation

Deliverable D1.3

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Description:

This report includes an overview of the educational leaflets and recommendations for patient recruitment, healthcare professional and strategic leaders/commissioners engagement.

Publishable summary

The aim of Work Package 1 (WP1) of STRONG AYA is to develop a Core Outcome Set (COS) for adolescents and young adults (AYAs) with cancer. With the initial COS domains and metrics nearing finalisation, WP1 is turning its attention to deliverable 1.3: data collection and implementation. To encourage participation in this next phase of the project, clear and concise educational materials (e.g. leaflets) are essential.

We describe the development of educational leaflets to support recruitment to the STRONG AYA project and recommendations for engagement with patients, healthcare professionals (HCPs) and strategic leaders/commissioners. Developed collaboratively with input from patients, HCPs and strategic leaders, these leaflets are designed with an informal tone for patients, a professional tone for healthcare professionals, and a strategic perspective for leaders/commissioners, ensuring appropriate communication with each stakeholder group.

Our recommendations for patient recruitment emphasise the importance of concise communication materials, and information sessions aimed at reaching a diverse audience. The use of social media platforms fosters a sense of community, while the active involvement of the Patient Advisory Board personalizes outreach efforts. Incentives, including gift cards and recognition in publications, could be used to thank participants for their invaluable contributions.

In engaging healthcare professionals, we recommend ensuring that data collection processes can be well integrated into existing workflows to minimize burden on busy HCPs. Professional development opportunities, and the importance of clinical champions to advocate for the initiative and encourage their colleagues to get involved could enhance engagement.

Our recommendations for securing support from strategic leaders and commissioners emphasise the project's alignment with organisational goals and financial viability. Regular updates and facilitated stakeholder meetings are key components in gaining buy-in and sustained commitment from these key stakeholders.

Together, these initiatives can encourage active participation and support, and ultimately contribute to meeting STRONG AYA's aim to improve patient-centred health research and outcomes for young people with cancer.

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2 Definitions

STRONG AYA consortium members are referred to as following within this text:

1. **NKI-AVL** – Stichting het Nederlands Kanker Instituut – Antoni van Leeuwenhoek Ziekenhuis (NL)
 2. **YCE** – Youth Cancer Europe (RO)
 3. **INT** – Fondazione IRCCS Istituto Nazionale dei Tumori (IT)
 4. **FFUND** – FFUND BV (NL)
 5. **CLB** – Centre de Lutte Contre le Cancer Leon Berard (FR)
 6. **ECO** – European Cancer Organisation (BE)
 7. **UNIMAAS** – Universiteit Maastricht (NL)
 8. **IKNL** – Stichting Integraal Kankercentrum Nederland (NL)
 9. **EORTC** – European Organisation for Research and Treatment of Cancer AISBL (BE)
 10. **IGR** – Institut Gustave Roussy (FR)
 11. **MSCNRIO** – Narodowy Instytut Onkologii im. Marii Skłodowskiej-Curie – Państwowy Instytut Badawczy (Marie Skłodowska-Curie National Research Institute of Oncology) (PL)
 12. **UOM** – University of Manchester (UK)
 13. **UOL** – University of Leeds (UK)
 14. **LTHT** – Leeds Teaching Hospitals National Health Service Trust (UL)
 15. **SOUTHAMPTON** – University of Southampton (UK)
- **Grant Agreement** (including its annexes and amendments): the agreement signed between the beneficiaries of the HORIZON Research and Innovations Actions (hereafter referred to as Horizon) and the European Health and Digital Executive Agency (hereafter referred to as HADEA) for the undertaking of the STRONG AYA project (Grant Agreement no. 101057482).
 - **Beneficiary**: Signatories of the Grant Agreement
 - **Associated Partner**: Entities which participate in the action but without the right to charge costs or claim contributions.
 - **Project**: the sum of all activities carried out in the framework of the Grant Agreement.
 - **Consortium**: the STRONG AYA consortium, including all the aforementioned partners.
 - **Consortium Agreement**: The agreement made between STRONG AYA members for the implementation and execution of the action outlined in the Grant Agreement. The agreement shall not affect the parties' obligations to HADEA on behalf of the European Union, and/or to one another arising from the Grant Agreement.

3 Abbreviations

Acronym/Abbreviation	Meaning
HCP	Healthcare Professional
PRO	Patient Reported Outcome
PROM	Patient Reported Outcome Measure
COS	Core Outcome Set
WP	Work Package
WPL	Work Package Lead(s)
WP1	Work Package 1 (Development Core Outcome Set AYA with cancer & data collection)
WP2	Work Package 2 (Governance, Data Security and Ethics)
WP3	Work Package 3 (Infrastructure and Interoperability)
WP4	Work Package 4 (Operation of STRONG AYA ecosystems, stakeholder and patient involvement, dissemination, exploitation, communication)
WP5	Work Package 5 (Scientific coordination and project management)
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
OA	Open Access
PAB	Patient Advisory Board
EC	European Commission
HADEA	European Health and Digital Executive Agency
SC	Steering Committee
MT	Management Team

4 Introduction

4.1 Project background

STRONG AYA is an EU-funded project that started in October 2022 and will run for 5 years, until 2027. The project aims to create a new, interdisciplinary, multi-stakeholder European network around an innovative data ecosystem to improve health care services, research, outcomes and policies for AYAs with cancer, which are defined for the project as individuals aged 15-39 years at cancer diagnosis.

Cancer at adolescent and young adult (AYA) age is rare; their annual cancer incidence is 42.2/100.000, with 156.431 cases in Europe and 1.231.007 cases worldwide reported in 2018 (together 6.8% of all cancers)³. Population-based data from 27 European countries supports that AYAs have lower survival than children but higher than adults affected by cancer. Advances in cancer treatment have led to increased survival rates for AYAs with cancer, improving by 82% for all cancers between 1990 and 2007⁴. However, this rarity does not reflect the significant personal and societal costs of cancer in this population, as reflected in the potential years of life lost or saved, the decreased productivity and quality of life due to the impact of the disease during formative years, and the long-term complications or disabilities¹. AYAs with cancer form a unique group; they face age-specific issues (e.g., infertility, unemployment, financial problems) and decreased quality of life due to cancer and its treatment. Unlike dedicated healthcare and trials for paediatric cancer patients, AYA-specific healthcare services are scarce and vary across Europe. AYAs who are at the core of society and economy need access to age-appropriate and high-quality healthcare.

AYA face some distinct challenges given that they do not belong to neither paediatric nor adult oncology groups. Characteristic features of this population group include unique spectrum of cancer types, different tumour biology, unique complex psychological needs, distinct late sequelae, including impaired fertility, and palliative care. These traits imply that clinical management, treatment, diagnosis, psychological support will need to be designed and developed for AYA's specific needs. For example, AYAs diagnosed with breast and prostate carcinomas have worse survival than older patients because of the biological differences between them, highlighting the need to target screening methodologies, treatment and policies to their needs⁶. AYAs with cancer also face significant psychological challenges, including substance abuse, mental health issues, suicidal ideations and increased emotional burden from cancer and cancer-related morbidity. Finally, tailoring cancer care to AYA's needs is difficult and due to many different complex factors including the low rate of participation by AYAs in clinical trials and cancer research⁷.

According to a survey conducted through the networks of the AYA Working Group of the European Society for Medical Oncology (ESMO) and the European Society for Paediatric Oncology (SIOP Europe), 67% of practitioners do not have access to specialised centres for AYA with cancer, 67% had no access to a specialist cancer service for late effects management and 38% had no access to fertility specialists. Under-provision and inequality of AYA cancer care is common across Europe and especially in the Eastern and Southern-East. Furthermore, the Working Group also reported an absence of outcome measures for monitoring and evaluating AYA cancer care programs and control¹³.

Among the recommended future steps, it has been identified that one of the most important contributions to AYA research would be to pool data (e.g. patient-reported outcomes, clinical and treatment data) across institutions and countries and create large cohorts for researchers to address the burden of cancer in AYAs¹⁴. There is a lack of data standardisation, data interoperability and (prospective) collection of outcomes of relevance for AYAs with cancer.

The STRONG AYA project aims to tackle the underrepresentation of AYA's experiences and outcomes when navigating the healthcare system and in clinical care by developing national infrastructures for outcome data management and clinical decision-making within a pan-European ecosystem and establishing communication feedback for AYAs with cancer and the healthcare systems. This will be key to improving

healthcare services, research, outcomes and policies for AYAs and to ultimately better cancer care for this patient group.

To this aim, STRONG AYA brings together an international multi-disciplinary consortium across seven European countries, led by the Netherlands Cancer Institute (NKI) and composed of academic research organisations (European Organisation for Research and Treatment of Cancer (EORTC), University of Southampton, University of Leeds, University of Manchester, Maastricht University, Netherlands Comprehensive Cancer Organisation (IKNL)), clinical partners (Italian National Tumour Institute, Léon Bérard Centre, Gustave Roussy Institute, Maria Skłodowska-Curie National Research Institute of Oncology, the Leeds Teaching Hospitals National Health Service Trust), stakeholder and patient organisations (Youth Cancer Europe, European Cancer Organisation) and a consulting company (FFUND).

Building on previous initiatives, a STRONG-AYA data ecosystem will be set up for value-based care, research and policy for AYA with cancer by:

1. **Developing a Core Outcome Set (COS)** specifically for AYAs with cancer, via a participative consensus process defining most important aspects for those directly affected by AYA cancer, including patients and healthcare professionals (WP1).
 - **Implementing the COS across several national European healthcare systems.** Data will be collected at local level and will then be included in a data integration platform. An overall ecosystem framework for data analytics and output will be created supporting federated analyses and the creation of reports across clinical and patient-reported data and making national repositories of (patient-reported) health data, available to individual patients, patient organisations, regulatory authorities, as well as the patients' health care providers to inform clinical decision-making. The five resulting **national ecosystems** will be connected to each other into **the pan-European ecosystem** using a federated approach also utilizing the overall ecosystem framework.
3. **Disseminating the COS to a wide range of local as well as pan-European stakeholders**, in particular by developing analytical tools to process and present patient outcome data and establish feedback loops that inform patients and clinicians.

STRONG AYA will enable AYA care and research to benefit from collection and pooling of patient-centered data and collaboration among all stakeholders: patients, healthcare professionals, scientists, and policymakers. More widely, the project will leverage the network of interested organisations and networks established under STRONG AYA for long-term strengthened promotion of the necessary implementation of specialist AYA cancer services across Europe. This will ultimately bring novel insights into AYA cancer care, research and policy, contributing to the long-term improvement of outcomes for people with AYA cancer.

4.2 Deliverable introduction

WP1 (developing a Core Outcome Set): The overall aim of WP1 is to develop a Core Outcome Set for AYAs with cancer. We aim to assess which outcomes including patient-reported outcomes, clinical, and treatment data, are most important to assess for AYAs with cancer, from the point of view of AYAs with cancer, healthcare professionals and other stakeholders, to arrive at a consensus. This will be done through three phases; 1) a review of the literature to identify relevant outcomes for AYAs with cancer, 2) qualitative interviews with AYAs with cancer/who have had a diagnosis of cancer, parents/partners/siblings and healthcare professionals who provide care to AYAs to generate a complete list of outcomes of relevance to AYAs with cancer, and 3) conducting a Delphi study. The Delphi technique is used for achieving convergence of opinion from all stakeholders (with equal contributions) on the importance of different outcomes in multiple anonymised prioritisation rounds. A three-round survey will be sent to stakeholders asking questions around outcomes relevant to AYAs cancer care ranking them based on perceived level of importance.

With the initial COS domains and metrics nearing finalisation, WP1 is turning its attention to D1.3: data collection and implementation. To encourage participation in this next phase of the project, clear and concise educational materials (e.g. leaflets) are essential.

This report outlines the purpose of the educational leaflets, why they were developed and how they were produced. We also report on recommendations for patient recruitment and engagement of clinicians and strategic leaders/commissioners.

5 Educational leaflets

In this report, we describe the development and purpose of three sets of educational leaflets designed to improve recruitment to the data collection and implementation phase of the STRONG AYA project. Designed with an informal tone, these leaflets underwent a collaborative design process involving patients from the Patient Advisory Board (PAB), researchers and healthcare providers (HCPs) within the STRONG AYA consortium. Initially created using Canva and enhanced with the help of a graphic designer, these leaflets are designed to complement existing Patient Information Form (PIF) documents to be provided by individual participating centres. The leaflets explain STRONG AYA, what data will be collected, how the data will be used, and the benefits to participants who take part.

Development Process

The three sets of educational leaflets, tailored for patients, healthcare professionals and strategic leaders/commissioners, were initially created on Canva (<https://www.canva.com/>). The leaflet is split into eight short sections of text; *What is STRONG AYA*, *What are we doing?*, *What information are we collecting?*, *Why are we collecting your information?*, *How will we use your information?*, *How you can get involved?*, *Data Privacy and ethics* and *How will this benefit me?* The writing style maintains a patient-friendly tone for patient leaflets, a professional tone for HCPs and a strategic perspective for leaders/commissioners, ensuring it's relevance for all intended audiences. A collaborative approach was taken to the development of these leaflets, seeking insights from patients, HCPs and strategic leaders/commissioners within the STRONG AYA consortium. Feedback from this extensive review process has been incorporated into subsequent revisions.

Content of leaflets

Patient leaflet (see appendix 1)

The patient leaflets explain the importance of contributing their data for this project. The review process, involving the Patient Advisory Board, ensures that the content of the leaflet resonates with the intended audience.

In addition, a dedicated section in the patient leaflet only encourages patients not only to participate in data collection, but also to actively co-design the digital platform. The digital platform serves as a tool of data collection of patient reported outcomes. Therefore, patients' involvement in shaping its features ensures that it meets their unique needs and preferences.

HCP (see appendix 2)

Leaflets for healthcare providers focus on encouraging engagement of young people taking part in this research initiative.

Strategic Leaders/Commissioners (see appendix 3)

Leaflets for strategic leaders and commissioners provide a strategic perspective on the importance of the Trusts involvement in this important research initiative.

6 Recommendations for patient recruitment, HCP and strategic leaders/ commissioners’ engagement

In this section we outline recommendations for optimising patient recruitment, engaging healthcare providers and involving strategic leaders and commissioners in the STRONG AYA project. These recommendations are directly linked to the development of educational leaflets to enhance recruitment efforts.

Patient
<p>Clear communication of STRONG AYA initiative and benefits to future cancer patients</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Develop clear and concise communication materials that emphasise the importance of the STRONG AYA initiative. • Clearly outline the impact of patient participation in shaping the future of cancer care/healthcare for young people.
<p>Social media campaigns</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Use social media platforms (i.e. STRONG AYA social media platforms etc) to share engaging content, updates about the initiative, reaching a wider audience and creating a sense of community.
<p>Patient advisory board involvement</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Actively involve members of the Patient Advisory Board in outreach activities.
<p>Incentives and recognition</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Offer incentives for participation, such as gift cards, access to educational resources, or acknowledgment in research publications. • Recognise the contributions of participants through newsletters and social media.

HCP
<p>Education for healthcare professionals</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Provide healthcare professionals with comprehensive educational materials about the STRONG AYA initiative. • Highlight the potential benefits of their involvement in advancing research and improving patient outcomes.

<p>Integration with clinical practice</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ensure that data collection processes seamlessly integrate into existing healthcare workflows, minimising the additional burden on busy healthcare professionals.
<p>Professional development opportunities</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Offer an accredited training session or workshop related to youth focused research, making it convenient for healthcare professionals to enhance their skills while contributing to the initiative. • Showcase how involvement aligns with their commitment to staying at the forefront of medical advancements in cancer care for young people.
<p>Regular communication channels</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Establish regular communication channels, such as newsletters or webinars, to keep healthcare providers informed about the progress of the initiative. • Solicit and address their feedback to ensure ongoing support.
<p>Clinical champions</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Identify and promote clinical champions within participating healthcare centres to advocate for the initiative and encourage their colleagues to get involved.
<p>Recognition of clinician contributions</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Recognise and appreciate the efforts of healthcare providers by highlighting their contributions in project updates, reports, or conferences.

<p>Strategic leaders/commissioners</p>
<p>Align with organisational goals</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Clearly demonstrate how the STRONG AYA initiative aligns with the strategic goals and mission of the organisation/Trust. • Highlight the potential positive impact on the community and the broader healthcare landscape.
<p>Stakeholder engagement</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Schedule meetings with strategic leaders and commissioners to discuss the initiative, address any questions, and seek their input on how to enhance its strategic value.
<p>Financial incentives</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Highlight potential financial incentives or returns on investment for the organisation, (e.g. increased research funding, or positive community relationships). • Showcase the initiative as an investment in the future of healthcare.
<p>Educational sessions</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Conduct tailored educational sessions or workshops for strategic leaders and commissioners. • Provide in-depth insights into the expected outcomes, and the significance of patient centred healthcare research.
<p>Regular progress updates</p>

- Keep strategic leaders and commissioners informed through regular progress updates and reports.
- Demonstrate transparency in sharing milestones, challenges, and achievements, reinforcing their ongoing involvement.

Recognition and publicity

- Acknowledge and publicly recognise the support of strategic leaders and commissioners in various communication materials.

7 Conclusion

In summary, our collaborative design process involving patients from the PAB, HCPs and strategic leaders/commissioners has resulted in tailored leaflets. Designed with an informal tone for patients, a professional tone for healthcare professionals and a strategic perspective for leaders/commissioners, these leaflets inform about the STRONG AYA initiative in language that resonates with each stakeholder group.

The recommendations for patient recruitment emphasise concise communication materials, and information sessions, ensures a broad audience is reached. The use of social media platforms creates a sense of community, while the active involvement of the Patient Advisory Board personalises outreach efforts. Incentives such as gift cards and recognition in publications aim to recognise the invaluable contributions of participants.

When engaging healthcare professionals, the focus is on practicality and seamless integration into existing workflows. Through professional development opportunities, streamlined processes and the importance of clinical champions, we highlight that participation in the STRONG AYA initiative is both feasible and rewarding for healthcare professionals.

The recommendations for securing support from strategic leaders and commissioners highlight the initiative's alignment with organisational goals and financial viability. By providing regular updates, and facilitating stakeholder meetings, we hope to encourage endorsement from strategic leaders and commissioners.

Active participation of patients, healthcare professionals and support of strategic leaders and commissioners is key. Through these efforts, we hope to improve recruitment and engagement.

8 APPENDICES

Adolescents and Young Adults

What is STRONG AYA?

STRONG AYA is an international project that aims to improve healthcare services, research and outcomes for adolescents and young adults (AYAs) with cancer, defined as individuals aged 15-39 years at cancer diagnosis.

What are we doing?

We've talked to young people with cancer, their families, doctors, and researchers worldwide to find out what matters most to young people in understanding and treating cancer for this age group. They told us about things like wanting to socialise, managing fertility concerns, dealing with 'chemo brain' and feeling heard by their doctors. We've taken all this information and condensed it into a simple list, which we call a Core Outcome Set.

Now, we're using this list to inform the next steps. We're collecting information from young people across healthcare systems in five European countries. Check out the '*what information are we collecting*' and '*how you can get involved*' sections to understand what information we're collecting and how you can help.

By understanding what is needed, we can personalise the care we provide to better match what young people really need.

What information are we collecting?

We are collecting information about your cancer experiences after diagnosis (e.g. symptoms), your health, and overall wellbeing.

Why are we collecting your information?

To improve cancer care services and life after diagnosis and treatment. Your input could shape the future of cancer care.

How will we use your information?

Information you offer us will be collected on a secure digital platform. Our intention is that you have the option to share your cancer experiences and personal knowledge with your health care team, if you wish. This can help gather insights into your health (e.g. symptoms) and overall wellbeing from diagnosis and beyond.

We are designing ways for you, plus others such as healthcare professionals, who hold the relevant permissions, to access and utilise the information without revealing individual identities. Your individual information is combined with those of other patients to create collective information. This collective information helps us understand trends, discuss improvements and provide evidence for clinical, research, and policy purposes.

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How you can get involved?

We will ask you to fill out a survey covering aspects of your cancer experiences and wellbeing, (such as symptoms, quality of life, sleep, diet and daily activities).

Your information can be collected in a variety of ways: by email, telephone or at your next clinic appointment. STRONG AYA is spread across five different healthcare systems so approaches may vary between hospitals.

Feel free to fill out the survey as many times as needed, but we kindly ask for at least one survey to be completed once a year.

For more details, please see the patient information provided.

We would like you to collaborate with us on designing and developing our digital platform. If you're interested in getting involved or just want more information, please get in touch with your local study coordinator.

Data privacy and ethics

We take privacy seriously. In STRONG-AYA, we strictly adhere to data protection, privacy and patient rights, following regulations such as EU GDPR and national guidelines.

The use of this platform has been checked and approved by the relevant health service and academic research ethics committees in the participating centres.

How will this benefit young people with cancer?

The information you share could help healthcare teams make personalized decisions to make sure the right type of support is provided.

Plus by monitoring healthcare quality in different countries, our aim is to work towards ensuring that everyone gets the best care- no matter where they live.

You're not just part of a community; you're part of a movement that's changing how we take care of young people after their cancer diagnosis.

So, get ready to see the positive changes coming your way!

STRONG AYA is funded by the European Union (Grant Agreement No. 101057482). The views expressed are solely those of the author(s) and do not necessarily reflect the opinions of the European Union or the Health and Digital Executive Agency (HADEA). The European Union and the granting authority cannot be held responsible for these views. This project is further supported by Innovate UK under grants 10038931, 10039273, 10041045, and 10044189.

Healthcare professionals

What is STRONG AYA?

STRONG AYA is an international project that aims to improve healthcare services, research and outcomes for adolescents and young Adults (AYA) with cancer, defined as individuals aged 15-39 years at cancer diagnosis.

What do we do?

We've been talking to young people with cancer, their families, doctors, and researchers worldwide to find out what's most important in understanding and treating cancer for this age group. They told us about things like wanting to socialize, managing fertility concerns, dealing with 'chemo brain,' and feeling heard by their doctors. We've put all this info into a simple list we call a Core Outcome Set (COS).

We're using the COS to help us with the next steps. We're collecting information from young people across healthcare systems in five European countries.

Check out the 'what information are we collecting' and 'how you can get involved' sections to understand what information we're collecting and how you can help. Our goal is to share what we've learned, encourage collaboration between different groups, and use smart tools to make sure healthcare professionals and researchers have the best information for deciding on age-appropriate care.

By understanding the specific needs of young people with cancer, we want to make sure the care provided really meets what they truly need.

What information are we collecting?

We are gathering information from AYAs, about their experience with cancer after diagnosis (e.g. symptoms), overall health and wellbeing.

Why are we collecting this information?

To improve cancer care services and quality of life after diagnosis and treatment for AYAs.

How will we use this information?

We're gathering information from AYAs through a secure digital platform. This platform will help AYAs and healthcare professionals like yourself share information and insights into the AYA's health (e.g. symptoms) and overall wellbeing from diagnosis and beyond.

Patient's individual information is combined with those of other patient's to create collective information so that no one is identifiable. This collective information helps us understand trends, discuss improvements and provide evidence for clinical, research, and policy purposes.

How you can get involved?

Healthcare professionals play a vital role in our work. You can encourage patients to complete the survey evaluating outcomes.

This can be done as many times as needed, but at least once a year.

The survey covers different aspects such as symptoms, quality of life, sleep, diet, and daily activities, to improve healthcare understanding and support.

Patient data can be collected in a variety of ways: by email, by telephone or at an appointment. STRONG AYA is spread across five different healthcare systems so practice may vary between hospitals.

For more details, please see the patient information provided.

How will this benefit me?

STRONG AYA aims to equip healthcare professionals by providing essential data for optimizing AYA cancer care.

This intends to support shared decision-making, monitor healthcare quality, enhance research data sharing, and delivers real-world evidence.

By sharing insights with policy-makers, we collectively work to address and reduce inequalities in AYA cancer care across Europe.

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Data privacy and ethics

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The use of this platform has been checked and approved by the relevant health service and academic research ethics committees in the participating centres.

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Commissioners and policymakers

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What do we do?

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We're using the COS to help us with the next steps. We're collecting information from young people across healthcare systems in five European countries. Check out the 'what information are we collecting' and 'how you can get involved' sections to understand what information we're collecting and how you can help.

Our goal is to share what we've learned, encourage collaboration between different groups, and use smart tools to make sure healthcare professionals and researchers have the best information for deciding on age-appropriate care.

By understanding the specific needs of young people with cancer, we want to make sure the care provided really meets what they truly need.

What information are we collecting?

We are collecting information from AYAs (aged 15-39 years), about their cancer experiences after diagnosis (e.g. symptoms), their health, and overall wellbeing.

Why are we collecting this information?

To improve cancer care services and quality of life after diagnosis and treatment.

How will we use this information?

We're collecting information from patients through a secure digital platform. This platform will help AYAs and healthcare professionals have the option to share information and get a better understanding into the AYA's health (e.g. symptoms) and overall wellbeing from diagnosis and beyond, should they wish.

Patient's individual information is combined with those of other patient's to create collective information so that no one is identifiable. This collective information helps us understand health trends, discuss improvements and provide evidence for clinical, research, and policy purposes.

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How you can get involved?

Encourage healthcare providers to facilitate patient participation in our annual survey, accessible online, on paper, or with assistance from our team in person, over the phone, or via secure video-chat.

This survey focuses on various aspects of health and wellbeing.

Data privacy and ethics

We take privacy seriously. In STRONG-AYA, we strictly adhere to data protection, privacy and patient rights, following regulations such as EU GDPR and national guidelines.

The use of this platform has been checked and approved by the relevant health service and academic research ethics committees in the participating centres.

How will this benefit me?

STRONG AYA aims to provide crucial insights into patient experiences and needs. This data aids in informed decision making for resource allocation, service improvement, and strategic planning.

The survey data will contribute to more effective and tailored healthcare services. This strategic approach ensures a more sustainable healthcare system that aligns with both patient needs and economic considerations.

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